

NOTES

Cobalt(II) Complexes with ONO Donor Tridentate Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Substituted Salicylaldehydes and Orthohydroxybenzylamine

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THERE has been considerable research interest in recent years in the metal complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases which force the metal (II and III) ions to give dimetallic complexes with novel magnetic properties^{1,2}. Most of these studies, however, are concerned with $S=1/2$ systems and little attention has been paid to other spin systems ($S=3/2, 5/2$). In continuation of our work^{1,2} on magnetic exchange properties of dimetallic complexes with $S=1/2$ or $5/2$, we describe here the syn-

1. X=H, 5-Chloro, 5-Nitro, 5-Bromo, 3-Methoxy, 3-Ethoxy, 3,5-Dichloro, 5,6-Benzo.

thesis of new dimetallic cobalt(II) complexes ($S=3/2$ system) of the Schiff bases (I). The complexes have been characterized on the basis of elemental analysis, conductance, molecular weight, magnetic susceptibility, ir and electronic spectral measurements.

Experimental

General method of synthesis of the complexes: Orthohydroxybenzylamine was prepared as described in the literature⁴. The appropriate Schiff base (0.004 mole) was dissolved in 10-15 ml of ethanol by heating on a waterbath. An ethanolic solution of cobalt(II) acetate tetrahydrate (1.08 g; 0.004 mole in 10 ml) was added to the yellow or orange Schiff base solution and the mixture refluxed for 3 hr. The separated precipitates were suction filtered, washed with warm ethanol followed by ether and dried under vacuum. Yield 55%.

The metal content was determined complexometrically by EDTA using eriochrome black-T an indicator. The electronic absorption spectra were recorded on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer

in methanol. Nitrogen analyses, conductance, molecular weight, infrared spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements were done as reported earlier⁵. The magnetic susceptibilities were corrected for TIP and diamagnetic contributions.

Results and Discussion

The complexes $[\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2(\text{BBB})]$ (where $\text{BBBH}_2 = \text{Schiff base, I}$) behave as non-electrolytes in methanol ($\Delta_M = 3.9 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$). The molecular weight data (Table 1) indicate that the complexes are dimers and they should be formulated as $[\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2(\text{BBB})]_2$. A shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) band of the ligand ($\sim 1540 \text{ cm}^{-1}$) to higher energy by $\geq 10 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ on complexation has been used as an unambiguous evidence for the formation of phenolic oxygen bridge in dimetallic complexes⁶. We have also observed such a position shift of the $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O})$ (phenolic) band indicating the presence of phenolic oxygen bridge. The presence of coordinated water is evident from the occurrence of a medium intense band at around 3200 cm^{-1} in the complexes⁷. The ligands (I) show a band at around 2700 cm^{-1} which is assigned to $\nu(\text{OH})$ of the intramolecularly hydrogen bonded OH group. This band is absent in the complexes, indicating the breaking of the hydrogen bonding and consequent deprotonation and coordination to the metal ion. The $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ stretch occurs at $1630-1660 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectra of the ligands and this band undergoes a negative shift in the complexes indicating nitrogen coordination of the azomethine moiety⁸.

The complexes exhibit three electronic spectral bands at around 800, 18000 and 22000 cm^{-1} with molar extinction coefficient (ϵ) in the range 18-24 litre mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. These bands are assigned to the ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(v_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{1g}(v_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P)(v_3)$ transitions respectively in an octahedral field⁹. The low ϵ values are in conformity with the characteristic of O_h symmetry cobalt(II) complexes. The electronic spectral data preclude the presence of a tetrahedral structure⁹.

The dimeric nature of these complexes suggests a μ -bis (Schiff base) tetraaquodicobalt(II), $[\text{Co}(\text{OH}_2)_2(\text{Schiff base})]_2$ with aquo molecules in the *trans* positions (cf. II) of the two O_h symmetry

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL, MOLECULAR WEIGHT, CONDUCTANCE, MAGNETIC MOMENT, INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA OF COBALT(II) COMPLEXES OF SCHIFF BASES^{a, b}

Complex/Stoichiometry	Found (Calcd.) %Co %N	Mol. wt. Found (Calcd.)	Λ_M ohm ⁻¹ cm ² mole ⁻¹	$\nu(C-O)$ complex (ligand)	$\nu(C=N)$ complex (ligand)	μ_{eff} B.M. (Temp.) °K	ν_{max} (ϵ)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (sal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₈ O ₈ N ₂ Co ₂	18.2 (18.44) 4.0 (4.88)	642 (640)	8.9	1540 (1530)	1615 (1657)	4.70	8790(18), 18180(18), 22470(23), 8770(21), 18690(21), 22220(24)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-chlorosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Co ₂	16.5 (16.64) 3.7 (3.95)	715 (709)	7.3	1530 (1515)	1620 (1660)	5.04	8770(21), 18690(21), 22220(24)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-bromosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₂ Br ₂ Co ₂	14.6 (14.79) 3.2 (3.51)	788 (798)	9.3	1535 (1515)	1620 (1655)	5.30	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (5-nitrosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₅ O ₈ N ₄ Co ₂	16.1 (16.16) 7.9 (7.67)	735 (730)	3.4	1540 (1530)	1635 (1640)	5.08	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3-methoxysal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₃₀ H ₂₈ O ₁₀ N ₂ Co ₂	16.8 (16.86) 4.3 (4.00)	705 (700)	9.6	1530 (1515)	1615 (1640)	4.95	8800(20), 18520(20), 21740(20)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3-ethoxysal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₃₂ H ₃₀ O ₁₀ N ₂ Co ₂	16.1 (16.21) 3.7 (3.85)	721 (728)	7.5	1540 (1530)	1625 (1660)	4.91	
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (3,5-dichlorosal-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₃ O ₈ N ₂ Cl ₂ Co ₂	15.0 (15.17) 3.3 (3.60)	775 (778)	5.5	1530 (1500)	1625 (1640)	4.92	8810(20), 18520(20), 22990(22)
[Co(OH ₂) ₂ (hydrox-OHYBA)] ₂ C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₈ N ₂ Co ₂	15.6 (15.95) 3.5 (3.78)	754 (740)	3.9	1550 (1530)	1610 (1630)	5.24	

- (a) Abbreviations : sal=salicylaldehyde, 5-chlorosal=5-chlorosalicylaldehyde ; 5-bromosal=5-bromosalicylaldehyde ; 5-nitrosal=5-nitrosalicylaldehyde ; 3-methoxysal=3-methoxysalicylaldehyde ; 3-ethoxysal=3-ethoxysalicylaldehyde ; 3,5-dichlorosal=3,5-dichlorosalicylaldehyde ; hydrox=2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and OHYBA=orthohydroxybenzylamine.
- (b) IR and electronic spectral bands are in cm⁻¹.

cobalt(II). The ir data, as discussed earlier, support this structure. The measured magnetic moments (Table 1) of the complexes are in the range 4.70-5.30 B.M. and are characteristic of magnetically dilute octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁹.

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Some Ligational Aspects of Tartrazine : Its Binary and Ternary Lanthanide Complexes

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TARTRAZINE is a basic azo-dye (Acid yellow CI 19140) used for dyeing food-stuffs and preservatives¹. It has also been used as a redox indicator² and as sodium salt in inks. It shows a yellow to purple colour change with pH, which may be used to explore the possibility of its being used as a metallochromic indicator. However, no attempt seems to have been made to study its complexes in solution.

The present work describes its binary complexes with La³⁺, Ce³⁺, Pr³⁺, Nd³⁺, Sm³⁺ and Gd³⁺ and ternary complexes with these metal ions using EDTA as a primary ligand.

Experimental

Standard solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving their nitrates (Fluka, AG) and oxides in double distilled water and perchloric acid, respectively, and excess of the acid was evaporated. 1 M sodium perchlorate (Riedel) solution was used to maintain the ionic strength at 0.2M. The dye, obtained from I. C. I., India, was further purified by recrystallization. A 0.2 N NaOH (Sarabhai M)